

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Hernández Vargas et al.

**A taxonomy for urban mining
of precast concrete**

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches the possibilities for deconstructing and reusing precast concrete elements from end-of-life buildings not originally designed for disassembly. This report explores a faceted classification approach to create a taxonomy of precast concrete elements and systems for reuse.

After World War II, precasting represented a major shift in concrete construction. Various precast systems were rapidly developed, and they spread throughout Europe and worldwide. Multiple actors, as well as political, economic, and cultural aspects, were involved, resulting in a wide variety of technologies and approaches that were developed independently of one another.

Today, the construction industry is transitioning from a traditional representation language (2D and 3D CAD drawings) to Building Information Modelling (BIM). In order to make salvaged precast elements available for reuse, old technologies must be translated into standardised digital formats to facilitate their inclusion in current digital workflows. Currently, the lack of a systematic approach to identifying, classifying, and reporting existing precast elements represents a major barrier to effectively integrating these elements in new building projects. Therefore, this report introduces a proposal of a classification taxonomy for precast concrete elements based on a faceted classification system. Unlike traditional hierarchical (enumerative) taxonomies, a faceted approach allows multiple classifications to be assigned to an object, enabling a more flexible characterisation by any combination of these facets.

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1. Introduction

In the mid-20th century, the mainstreaming of precast concrete elements and large-panel systems marked the shift from traditional labour-intensive construction methods to off-site prefabrication. This shift required standardisation of building components, systematisation of labour, and introduction of machines and production lines that significantly reduced the construction time and costs.

While early precast systems were developed as a comprehensive set of elements designed for a specific purpose, further modularisation and standardisation of elements gave rise to increased flexibility. For example, in Germany, precast systems transitioned from block and strip construction to large-panel prefabrication, which increased in size over time (Mettke, 1990). In Finland, after some experiments in the 1940s, the use of precast concrete for building construction started in earnest at the turn of the 1950s (Huuhka et al., 2015). Initially, precast components were used mostly for non-residential buildings, with the first fully prefabricated large panel-based block of flats constructed in 1959. By the early 1960s, major construction companies had transitioned to panel construction, with each company developing their own system, most often influenced by French, Swedish, or Danish systems (Hytönen & Seppänen, 2009). Toward the late 1960s, the Finnish concrete industry initiated a project to establish a unified, standardised panel system as a single national standard ('BES'), which was flexible enough to build different building types (Seppänen & Koivu, 1970). Similar systems emerged in other countries, and especially in Eastern Europe, often with a strong influence from Soviet systems, which were applied and adapted to different contexts.

The development of precast concrete systems is fragmented because of different national policies and the involvement of several actors in a wide range of contexts. Cross-border interactions took place in the form of systems that were sold as patents, or sometimes as whole factories (Alonso et al., 2019). As the industry evolved, it moved from closed precast systems (i.e. factory-specific systems, the details of which were considered industrial secrets) to more flexible and tailored solutions, allowing precast elements to be combined more freely with other components. Subsequently, dedicated standards (e.g. SS EN 1168) were developed for elements like hollow-core slabs.

Like the taxonomy of biological organisms, tracing historical links can help understand the development of different systems across various countries, often revealing shared origins and shared features. Many systems are based on similar technical constraints and engineering principles, but direct connections also exist, like transferring expertise, patents, and entire factories between countries (Alonso, 2019). This historical background can help to understand common patterns and complete missing information between related systems. However, not all systems followed a uniform evolutionary path. Many precast systems and factories were developed in isolation, making the tracing of historical genealogies less relevant.

This report is part of ReCreate's Work Package 1 (WPI), which focuses on the historical development of precast concrete in Europe by mapping, ordering, classifying and compiling a database of precast elements and systems. The taxonomy in this report is based on the historical research from Stenberg et al. (2025), which maps precast systems from eleven EU countries. Archival research has been organised into country dossiers, timelines, and a consolidated European digital map. Conversely, the taxonomies and naming systems developed in this report are used to index and structure the information collected in the dossiers and contribute to the database structure of the map. This report further expands on precast concrete element typologies developed in Hernández Vargas & Stenberg (2024).

The classification system proposed in this report has been developed in the ReCreate project through several workshops and project meetings within the project consortium. First, a historical background was developed for each of the ReCreate deconstruction pilots (see Vullings et al. 2024), providing a general background and technical details about the donor buildings and the systems and manufacturers involved. Further historical sources were researched extensively in each country in the local language. The research focused on assembling information from diverse sources, including technical reports, industry guidelines, and historical documentation, to create a structured and accessible reference.. These tasks and reports were also developed in coordination with other parts of the ReCreate project. In particular, they consider the requirements for pre-deconstruction audits (Vullings et al., 2022), quality assurance (Räsänen et al., 2024), and logistics and processing (Dervishaj & Gudmundsson, 2025). The proposed classification system will also serve as the basis for structuring an element database of precast elements, which will be documented in ReCreate's upcoming Deliverable D1.4, *Database with Digital Models of Precast Concrete Elements*.

The aim of the report

This report focuses on developing a systematic classification system for precast systems and elements. Its main objective is to establish a structured framework for categorising precast elements and systems that facilitate the identification and documentation of existing precast buildings as a source of components for future reuse projects. Given the large diversity of precast elements developed in different contexts, this study aims to provide a structured methodology for the further expansion of documented sources. By defining categories and properties, this report provides guidelines for the structure of databases of precast elements and systems for reuse. Precast systems and elements from the national ReCreate dossiers (Stenberg et al., 2025) are further categorised following the definitions outlined in this document, thereby facilitating urban mining strategies for precast concrete reuse.

Structure of the report

Chapter 2 provides an overall introduction to taxonomic systems, comparing hierarchical and faceted approaches to classification and examining their advantages and limitations. Following this, Chapter 3 provides a detailed examination of the proposed faceted classification system, breaking down its components and their interrelations. Real-world

applicability is demonstrated in Chapter 4 through case studies that highlight the practical implementation of the taxonomy. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes the report by summarising the key findings and proposing directions for future research.

2. On taxonomic systems

'To classify' is to organise objects into classes according to criteria (SS-ISO 22274, 2013). In this definition, an object can be anything imaginable, while a class is a description of a set of objects that share some common characteristics or features. More broadly, classification implies arranging and systematising knowledge that uncovers or imposes order into the world. By establishing taxonomies, classification provides a framework through which patterns can be identified, relationships can be mapped, and knowledge can be systematically expanded.

Beyond practical implications, classification is strongly linked to fundamental ideas of epistemology and how humans perceive and understand the world. Since the early Aristotelian tradition, the idea of types and archetypes has been fundamental for the development of categories and concepts. A foundational example of this problem is discussed by Michel Foucault (1994) referring to a story by Jorge Luis Borges, '*Celestial Emporium of Benevolent Knowledge*', which presents a fictional taxonomy, allegedly taken from an old Chinese encyclopaedia. This taxonomy categorises animals into fourteen seemingly arbitrary groups, such as '*those that belong to the Emperor*', '*embalmed ones*', '*mermaids*', and so on. The last categories include '*etcetera*' and '*those that from afar look like flies*'. This fictional taxonomy illustrates the arbitrary nature of classification and highlights the cultural and contextual influences on classification systems.

Modern computer science has significantly contributed to the refinement of classification frameworks, laying the foundation for standardised information management in digital environments. In the building sector, the development of industry-wide standards has been crucial in structuring and integrating data across various domains, particularly in Building Information Modelling (BIM). These classification systems do not merely categorise reality; they establish rules that define how information is stored, accessed, and interpreted. In BIM, structured classification standards ensure interoperability, data consistency, and efficient collaboration across disciplines, facilitating seamless information exchange in complex construction projects. As a result, these classification systems have become essential tools in digital management systems, shaping digital workflows and influencing how reality is conceptualised and processed in engineering and architectural applications.

2.1. Historical development of classification systems

Throughout the history of biology, the classification of the natural world has evolved through three main approaches – artificial, natural, and phylogenetic – as criteria for grouping organisms. Artificial classification systems were among the first approaches to categorise objects and ideas. These systems were based on readily observable traits, such as size, colour, or shape, allowing for quick and straightforward sorting. While practical in many

cases, they can often oversimplify relationships between objects by ignoring deeper connections. For example, classifying animals based solely on their number of legs may group organisms that are not closely related, leading to inconsistencies when applied to more complex or evolving domains.

In 1735, Carl von Linné published his book *Systema Naturae* (Linné, 1748), wherein he introduced a systematic and hierarchical taxonomy to classify plants, animals, and minerals. Hierarchical taxonomies were extensively used in natural history and became the foundation of modern biology. Linnaean taxonomy organises living organisms into nested groups based on shared physical characteristics, encompassing kingdom, class, order, family, genus, and species. A key innovation of this system is the use of a binomial nomenclature, where a two-part Latin name is assigned to each species consisting of its genus and species identifiers (as exemplified in Figure 1). This naming convention provides a standardised reference across languages and disciplines.

Kingdom: *Plantae*
Class: *Magnoliopsida*
Order: *Lamiales*
Family: *Lamiaceae*
Genus: *Ocimum*

Species:
Ocimum basilicum

EN Basil
FI Basilika
SV Basilika
DE Basilikum
NL Basilicum

Figure 1. Example of the binomial classification system used in the natural sciences. The two-part Latin name specifies the genus and species and serves as a uniform name across different languages. Illustration by Elizabeth Blackwell, 1739 (public domain).

Natural classification systems, on the other hand, are designed to reflect inherent relationships between objects. Instead of relying on surface-level traits, these systems seek to capture essential characteristics that define how objects are related. Because natural classifications align with the fundamental nature of objects, they provide a stronger foundation for scientific research and practical applications over time.

The proposition of the theory of evolution by Charles Darwin in the 19th century provided a further temporal dimension to the definition of species. Instead of static types, species are now seen as dynamic entities, defined by the existence of common ancestors (Figure 2).

With further advances in genetics, scientists developed phylogenetic classification, which maps out evolutionary relationships rather than grouping organisms based solely on physical similarities. Whereas the principles that distinguish separate plant and animal species led to the definition of these clear hierarchical structures, these boundaries are blurred when applied to other types of organisms, such as fungi and bacteria. By comparing genetic material, researchers can trace common ancestors and evolutionary pathways, creating a dynamic and interconnected view of the natural world. This approach allows for a more flexible and accurate understanding of species, accounting for gradual changes and adaptations over time.

The development of classification systems is not limited to the biological sciences. For instance, the Encyclopaedia of Chess Openings (*Chess Openings - Encyclopedia of Chess Openings*, 2008) represents a hierarchical classification system, organising chess strategies into a structured scheme. Similarly, library indexing systems utilise hierarchical classification to structure vast amounts of information in an accessible manner. Classification systems structure knowledge within a domain to facilitate the handling and interpretation of objects by ensuring unambiguous characterisation (SS-ISO 22274, 2013).

A classification system can be enumerative, faceted or a combination of the previous two (SS-ISO 22274, 2013). Enumerative classification systems aim to list all possible classes within a defined domain, typically using hierarchical structures. In contrast, faceted classification systems allow multiple classifications to be assigned to an object, enabling flexible characterisation through different facets. A hybrid approach combines both methods, usually using an enumerative structure at higher levels to define broad categories and a faceted approach at lower levels to specify the nature of individual concepts within the classification system.

Figure 2. Historical representations of the species classification systems. Left: Haeckel's tree of life in *Generelle Morphologie der Organismen* (1866) (Haeckel, 1866). Right: Darwin's representation of taxonomic order, *On the Origin of Species* (1859) (Darwin, 1979). Both images public domain.

2. 2. Enumerative classification systems

As said, enumerative classification systems aim to list all possible subjects within a defined scope, often organising them into hierarchical structures. However, in certain cases, these systems may also be represented as simple, unstructured sets of objects without hierarchical relationships. For example, the shape of a precast concrete element is developed and optimised to resist certain load criteria and other requirements. Therefore, while concrete elements can be classified based only on their shape, where their dominant dimensions provide a hint of their structural roles, the reinforcement limit the scope of applications.

Enumerative classification systems offer several advantages, primarily their simple and intuitive structure, which makes them easy to navigate and apply. Their hierarchical organisation allows users to categorise information in a systematic way, making them especially effective for well-defined domains where items fit neatly into single categories. However, these systems also come with limitations. They lack flexibility, particularly when dealing with items that belong to multiple categories, leading to rigid structures that may not accommodate emerging or overlapping classifications. As the complexity of categories increases, retrieval can become cumbersome, and users may struggle to locate specific items. Furthermore, enumerative classification systems often resort to general categories, such as 'Miscellaneous', to accommodate instances that do not fit neatly into the established framework, the hierarchical nature of enumerative classification may not always align well with real-world construction systems, causing mismatches and inefficiencies in classification applications (SS-ISO 22274, 2013).

2. 3. Faceted classification systems

Unlike hierarchical taxonomies, faceted categories provide a more flexible approach by organising information into multiple semantic categories, allowing systems to be classified across various dimensions or facets. A facet is a group of classes or concepts that share the same characteristics (SS-ISO 22274, 2013), allowing related attributes to be grouped into independent facets. Each facet represents a different dimension (such as author, subject, or format), and users can combine these facets in various ways to retrieve information efficiently.

For a faceted classification system to be effective, it must follow several key principles to ensure clarity, flexibility, and usability (SS-ISO 22274, 2013). These facets must be orthogonal, i.e., their areas of application should not intersect. At the same time, facets should be mutually exclusive while collectively covering all potential classification scenarios, ensuring completeness without ambiguity. Scalability is also essential—new categories must be easily incorporated without disrupting existing classifications, allowing the system to evolve alongside industry needs. They also should align with existing classification standards to enable integration with digital tools and knowledge management systems. A user

perspective is also to be taken into consideration, ensuring they are intuitive and practical for information retrieval.

Classification systems in construction organise vast amounts of project information into a hierarchical framework that facilitates communication, data exchange, and interoperability across different stages of a project's life cycle. For instance, Uniclass (2015) is a unified system developed in the UK that structures information via a suite of interrelated tables. Each table represents a different facet of construction data, such as complexes, entities, spaces, elements, systems, and products, and uses a multi-part alphanumeric code to describe an object from its most general grouping down to specific details. This approach is aligned with ISO 12006-2, which provides the overall framework for classifying building information throughout design, construction, and operation.

In contrast, CoClass (2025), developed in Sweden, is based on the ISO/IEC 81346 series. It adopts a more faceted approach by using a Reference Designation System (RDS) that assigns codes according to the function, technical system, and component attributes. This system emphasises a stable and unambiguous identification of elements across the entire life cycle of a construction project, ensuring that the same object retains a consistent code even as its detailed description evolves.

In Sweden, the naming of precast elements is based on a systematic industry convention based on a sequence of letters and numerical dimensions. Letters stand for features, element types, and variations, standing for commonly agreed-upon meanings in different parts of the acronym. For example, a hollow-core slab is referred to in Swedish documents as HD/F, where the H stands for a hollow cross-section (Hål), D stands for a slab element (Däck), and F stands for a pre-stressed (Förespänt) element. These letter codes are generally followed by numbers representing key dimensions, such as width and height, providing a concise and comprehensive description of the element characteristics and structural properties. Figure 3 shows an example of this nomenclature in an industry catalogue while Annex 7.2 details the full list of letter meanings as established by the industry in 1981.

Similarly, in Finland, identification codes are assigned to different element classes, combining a letter designation for the element type with a unique numerical identifier for a particular element type with fixed parameters. The numerical part indicates the element's location, including its floor and section. For example, RK-2201, where 'RK' denotes an internal shell element, '2' represents building segment 2, '2' indicates floor 2, and '01' is the element type number. It is recommended that a further number be added to specify each unique element instance (e.g. RK-2201-01). Annex 7.3 shows the table with letter codes for various element types. Since multiple identical elements may be used in a project, it is recommended to implement a separate sequential ID system to ensure the unique identification of each individual element (Betonia, 2023).

Figure 3. Swedish catalogue of beam elements. The RBK denomination on the right stands for a Rektangulär (rectangular) Balk (beam) för Kontinuitet (for structural continuity).
Reproduced from A-Betong (1974).

3. Proposed classification system

The proposed classification system distinguishes between general classes and specific instances of precast elements. A class represents the generic definition of a precast element defined by the manufacturer, while an instance refers to an actual, context-specific realisation of that class. By establishing a centralised database, each precast element can be tracked from its generic ‘class-level’ specification to its physical ‘instance-level’ object, including information such as survey data, quality assurance, and test results.

When applying these classification schemas to a workflow for reuse, the element class refers generically to all elements produced under the same specifications and sharing a common label. In a BIM environment, these elements are modelled from the same family but represent the class without referring to any individual instance. These ‘**blank elements**’ can be used as families to model the precast system in question. However, when these blank elements are individualised with an ID, location, production year, and other physical properties, they become specific instances of the class. Such ‘**donor building elements**’ are stored in a database as digital counterparts of actual physical elements. They can be used and tracked throughout the design process as reused elements. This workflow is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The overall workflow for the classification of elements. ‘Blank elements’ are built based on the technical details gathered from the dossiers. These elements are then assigned a specific identification, location, and other surveying parameters to represent a particular instance of a physical element, i.e. a ‘donor building element.’

This structured approach ensures a clear distinction between stable design definitions and dynamic variations of real-world objects, maintaining a consistent flow of information across different project and life cycle stages. Furthermore, a concept-based classification approach, where elements transition from conceptual definitions to final 'as-built' records in a traceable manner, allows each element to inherit relevant metadata from the element class (i.e. blank element) and accumulate new attributes (e.g. material properties or defects) as it progresses through testing, design, refurbishment, and reuse. For example, an element type is defined within a system as 'V2', denoting a wall element with specific dimensions. This definition often allows for minor variations of the same element. For example, elements produced from the same mould and production line but with different detailing or treatments may result in element 'V2a'.

The classification system for the reuse of precast concrete elements proposed in this report builds on existing BIM standards and construction classification systems. It is defined as a class system and a classification that provides the basis for specific BIM implementations. A fundamental aspect of this implementation is its adherence to international standards for data management and classification, like ISO 19650 (*SS-EN ISO 19650-1*, 2019), which governs information management in collaborative BIM environments. This ensures that project stakeholders can efficiently exchange structured data throughout the lifecycle of construction projects, enhancing coordination and reducing errors. The organisation of construction-related information follows the framework established in ISO 12006-2 (ISO, 2020b), which provides a schema for categorising building elements, materials, and processes. By utilising this structured approach, the classification system ensures consistency in how information is recorded and retrieved, supporting efficient project documentation and seamless integration with digital workflows. The ISO 12006 standard is, in turn, based on the more general principles of classification established by the standard *SS-ISO 22274* (2013). This ensures the system can be effectively used in international projects, facilitating collaboration across different linguistic and regulatory contexts. The alignment with this standard also enhances compatibility with existing industry taxonomies, such as the previously mentioned CoClass (2025), facilitating seamless data exchange across platforms and stakeholders.

The proposed taxonomy is based on a hybrid classification system. It mainly uses faceted classifications, but the categories on each facet are structured with enumerative schemas that allow for hierarchical sorting of the classified elements and systems (Figure 5). Facets are assigned alphanumeric codes that serve as indexed standard names for systems and factories. These codes are created once and added to a centralised database to ensure consistency and traceability across different projects and applications. Each facet corresponds to an individual attribute, such as structural principle, country of origin, or manufacturer. Distinct sets of facets are proposed for element and system classification. These codes can be embedded directly into filenames, stored within the metadata of digital files, and/or stored separately within the Common Data Environment (CDE). Since naming conventions vary between different BIM standards, the proposed naming system is not a substitute for international or national classification systems, for example, the proposals discussed in Dervishaj & Gudmundsson (2025).

Figure 5. Example of a faceted classification system for slabs. Each facet specifies a characteristic of the object, but these have an enumerative (hierarchical) classification scheme. The order of the facets can be arbitrary.

The precast taxonomy aims to provide the missing details not typically found in a classification system, such as factory, year of production, and type, among others, which are intended for the blank element database. Following BIM workflows, the information proposed in the next section must also be captured in a table in the file’s metadata (as a property set) or stored within the project’s CDE (Dervishaj et al., 2023). As the complete documentation may be missing in some cases, a special code (**UNK**) should be reserved for unknown data. Additionally, qualifiers may be appended to flag data uncertainty, using a **tilde (~)** before the value to indicate estimated or best-guess data, i.e. **~CODE**.

3. 1. Element facets

The classification of precast concrete elements presents significant challenges due to the inherent ambiguity between geometric and functional categories. Precast elements can be classified according to their geometry and proportions into three categories: blocks, panels, and linear elements (Hernández Vargas & Stenberg, 2024). Elements with a single predominant dimension, including posts and beams, are classified as linear elements. Room-sized components with two extended dimensions, such as slabs and walls, are designated panels. Meanwhile, components that are relatively thick and short are categorised as blocks. However, this purely geometric classification has limited applicability in the definition of structures. Whereas beams and columns share geometric similarities and can therefore be classified as ‘linear elements’, they serve fundamentally different structural functions that lead to separate classifications. For example, beams primarily resist bending forces while columns predominantly carry axial compression.

To ensure precise identification within the classification system, each element must contain a minimum of standardised information. This structured data captures key attributes that differentiate components within the taxonomy. The proposed faceted classification system for precast elements is designed to connect elements to their corresponding documentation in original archives, ensuring traceability throughout their lifecycle. Thus, the taxonomical code assigned to each element enables users to retrieve detailed documentation specific to a manufacturer, production facilities, and fabrication period.

The naming convention is based on the addition of the facets separated by underscores (_) and following the format:

[element_type]_[country_code]_[manufacturer_code]-[factory_code]_[production_year]_[local_code]

Figure 6. Example of the naming convention for element taxonomies.

Each part of the string corresponds to a different facet (Table 1). The first facet is the **element_type**, which is captured by a short code derived from the main precast element categories discussed in Hernández Vargas & Stenberg (2024). It is worth noting that these categories are limited to overall element categories, including a code for special elements (**X**), as shown in Table 2. The **country_code** facet follows the ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 standard (ISO, 2020a). This code identifies the national context of an element, which can influence material specifications, regulatory compliance, and design codes. Annex 7. 1 shows the countries included in the project scope, either as member or target countries. The origin of the element is specified by **manufacturer_code** and **factory_code** facets.

The process of creating and maintaining standardised manufacturer and factory codes follows a structured approach to ensure consistency, traceability, and interoperability across different construction projects. Each manufacturer is assigned a unique alphanumeric code, derived from its name. Similarly, factories are designated with a similar identifier. For example, the Swedish manufacturer Skånska Cementgjuteriet is represented as **SCG**, while **SCG-MI** refers to its first factory in Märsta. These codes should be stored in a centralised index, allowing efficient retrieval and ensuring uniqueness when referencing manufacturers and their production facilities. Within the CDE, the codes should be made available to users to validate that the codes in BIM properties or file names are correct and conform to the established taxonomy. Interested readers are referred to the guidelines for Common Data Environments proposed for the project consortium (Dervishaj & Gudmundsson, 2025).

The **production_year** provides a timestamp to locate the element within the factory production records. However, the production year may be gathered from different sources, which should be appended after the code using **F** (factory production), **P** (building permit), or **C** (construction completion). For example, **1975F** denotes factory production. Finally, the **local_code** captures the original terminology used in the documentation, preserving historical naming conventions while linking them to standardised identifiers in the classification system. The code is composed of the System code followed by the identifier of the element, e.g. the hollow core slab listed as B39 in the Swedish A-System is listed as **ASYS-B39**.

Additionally, supplementary metadata fields provide a means to reference more detailed documentation files when necessary, offering further insights into specific attributes or historical records. Real-world properties such as material composition, geometric specifications, and installation details are systematically stored and can be retrieved using Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) models or other digital tracking systems. A Global Unique Identifier (GUID) must be assigned when a blank element becomes a particular physical element. This identifier ensures that each element is uniquely labelled and tracked throughout its lifecycle. However, as GUIDs most commonly change with every export in BIM tools, these need to be updated regularly to ensure data consistency. For this, timestamps allow maintaining chronological records for version control and tracking of changes over time.

Table 1. Facets for element classification.

Facet	Data type	Constraints	Example	Explanation
Element Type	String (2-char)	Two-character code (Table 2)	SH	Slab / Hollow
Country code	String	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2	SE	Sweden
Manufacturer	String	Unique identifier for manufacturers	ABTG	A-Betong
Factory	String	Unique identifier for factories	STRN	Strängnäs
Production Year	Integer + letter	Year and a single-letter code Indicating the source of the date: F = factory production P = building permit C = construction	1998F	F = factory production
Local code	String	Original naming in the documentation	ASYS-B39	A-System - Bjälklag (Slab) 39M (3900 mm)

Table 2. Short codes for element type facets. These categories are based on the categories from the fib bulletin no. 74 (van Acker et al., 2014) and discussed in Hernández Vargas & Stenberg (2024).

Element	Subcategory	Code
Column (C)	Circular	CC
	Rectangular	CR
	Custom profile	CX
Beam (B)	Rectangular	BR
	L-shape	BL
	Inverted T	BT
	I-beam	BI
	Variable	BV
Wall (W)	Internal	WI
	Facade	WF
	Parapets	WP
Slab/Roof (S)	Solid	SS
	Hollow-core	SH
	Ribbed	SR
	Composite	SC
Stair (T)	Straight	TS
	Spiral	TC
	Monoblock	TM
Foundation (F)	-	F
Special elements (X)	-	X

3. 2. Structural system facets

In general, systems are collections of interrelated elements that function together to perform a certain function. For precast concrete systems, this set includes not only the collection of precast elements but also the plans, details, and other technical specifications that define the possible arrangements of the system for different building types. The proposed faceted classification aims to provide a framework for entire systems in addition to individual elements. However, the boundaries of a system are not always clearly defined. They often exhibit regional and temporal variations, much like the classification challenges found in biological taxonomy.

The broader mapping of precast concrete elements in Europe (Stenberg et al., 2025) has revealed that many systems belong to a broader series, maintaining similarities across multiple iterations while evolving over time. This definition is straightforward in closed industrialised systems, i.e. a set of elements and plans that enable a certain number of building types to be constructed with this system and is not meant to be combined with other components. In this case, the building is an object belonging to the system class in

the same way a certain individual is an instance of a certain species. Here, it is important to differentiate between types and instances. It is worth noting that despite the proposed unified classification scheme, elements from different systems within the same category may not always be compatible. This also applies to elements from the same system which are not designed to be used together. Variations in design specifications and intended applications can lead to inconsistencies that require case-specific solutions. The naming convention for the systems is composed of the following facets (see also Table 3):

[structural_principle]_[building_typology]_[country_code]_[manufacturer_code]-[factory_code]_[system_name]-[system_variation]_[production_year]

Figure 7. Example of the naming convention for system taxonomies.

The **structural_principle** facet captures the fundamental load-bearing concept of a system according to the main principles discussed in the Handbook for precast concrete (van Acker et al., 2014), represented by two-letter codes as shown in Figure 8. Similarly, **building_typology** identifies the function of a structure, classifying buildings into standardised categories such as residential or industrial applications (Table 4 & Figure 9). This facet is defined as an enumerative classification of material sources in the built environment specified in the classification of the anthropogenic stocks developed by Lanau et al. (2019), which is also discussed in Hernández Vargas & Stenberg (2024). This enumerative classification of the building stock was developed as part of the COST Action ‘Mining the European Anthroposphere’ (MINEA), which focused on assessing anthropogenic resources mirroring existing practices for natural deposits. As in the element facets, the **country_code** is specified using ISO1366-2 code.

Further classification includes the **manufacturer_code** and **factory_code** facets, uniquely identifying the production entity and specific manufacturing location. These attributes facilitate the tracking of production sources and correlate testing between elements with the same origin. The **system_name** facet assigns a unique identifier to each precast system, distinguishing it within the classification framework. This facet may include a **system_variation** modifier that defines subcategories or variations within a system. A general principle is to classify systems into groups as large as possible, using variations only when necessary. This facet is facultative and is separated with a hyphen (-) instead of an underscore to create a compound name consistent with established naming conventions used in several systems. For example, WBS-70 stands for *wohnungsbauserie* (residential building series) developed during the 1970s. Finally, the **production_year** facet records the building completion date, where the documentation should establish

acceptable ranges for each system. Like the element facets, the data source should be specified with a letter code.

Analogous to the element facets, manufacturer, factory, and system codes are assigned a unique identifier based on a predefined naming convention, ensuring systematic indexing and preventing duplication. These codes are stored in a centralised database, allowing for efficient retrieval and accurate tracking of production sources.

Table 3. Facets for system taxonomy

Facet	Data type	Constraints	Code	Explanation
Structural Principle	String (2-char)	Defines the core structural concept	CW	Wall frame / Cross wall
Building Typology	String (2-char)	Enumerated classification of building types	RE2	Residential / Multi-family
Country Code	String (2-char)	According to ISO 3166-1 alpha-2	SE	Sweden
Manufacturer	String	Unique producer identifier	SCG	SCG – Skånska Cementgjuteriet
Factory	String	Unique factory identifier	MI	Märsta I
System Name	String	Unique four-letter system identifier	HSB	Hälsingborg System
Variation	String	Defines subcategories of systems (optional)	16M	16M module
Production Year	Integer + letter	Must be a valid calendar year. Single-letter code indicating the source of the date: F = factory production P = building permit C = construction completion	1973F	F = factory production

Figure 8. Two-letter codes for describing the structural principle of precast structures. These categories are based on the fib Bulletin no. 74 (van Acker et al., 2014). The more general wall-frame (WF) code can be used when the specific structural configuration.

Table 4. Short codes for building typology facets

	Category	Facet	Code
	Residential	Single-family	RE1
		Multi-family	RE2
		Low-rise	RE2L
		High-rise	RE2H
		Other residential	RE3
Non-residential	Industrial	Manufacturing	IN1
		Supply & energy	IN2
		Agriculture	IN3
	Commercial	Retail	CM1
		Offices	CM2
		Storage	CM3
	Institutional	Education & research	IS1
		Health	IS2
		Governmental	IS3
		Recreational	IS4
	Transport	Parking houses	TR1
		Aviation buildings	TR2
		Port buildings	TR3
Stations		TR4	

Figure 9. Enumerative classification of the built environment based on the categories outlined by Lanau et al. (2019). The categories in green are the most relevant for ReCreate.

4. Case studies

This chapter demonstrates the application of the proposed faceted taxonomies on precast systems, other than those of ReCreate’s donor buildings.

4.1. Sweden: A-system

Råslätt, Jönköping

CW_RE2_SE_ABTG-VIS_ASYS_1968C

Figure 10. The Råslätt neighbourhood is built using the A-System precast system. Left: Photo of a A-System building (KTH/Erik Stenberg). Right: Plan and elevation. Reproduced from Wallinder (1969).

Facet	Explanation	Code
Structural principle	Cross-wall	CW
Building typology	Residential (multi-family)	RE2
Country code	Sweden	SE
Manufacturer	A-Betong	ABTG
Factory	Factory in Vislanda in Alvesta Municipality, Kronoberg County	VIS
System name	A-system	ASYS
Production year	Building completion year 1968 is used	1968C

The Råslätt Neighbourhood Jönköping, Sweden (**SE**), is a residential area designed by the architect Lars Stalin in **1968**. The dwellings are built with transverse load-bearing walls, i.e. a cross-wall frame (**CW**), with hollow-core slabs spanning a maximum of 3.9 m, though the system has a maximum span of 5.416 m. This area was developed using the open precast concrete system A-system (**ASYS**) by the company A-Betong (**ABTG**) and the elements were manufactured in the Vislanda (**VIS**) factory.

4. 2. Finland: BES

Kirstintie 17, Espoo, Finland

CW_RE2_FI_HAKA-VPK_BES_1977C

Figure 11. Top-left: plan drawing. Bottom-left: south-east elevation. Both reproduced from Espoo city archive (Espoon kaupunginarkisto). Right: archival photograph (1980s). Adapted from Kalliomäki, T., Suvelan kerrostaloalue 1980-luvulla. KAMU.

Facet	Explanation	Code
Structural principle	Cross-wall	CW
Building typology	Residential (multi-family)	RE2
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Haka Oy	HAKA
Factory	Factory in Piispankylä district in the municipality of Vantaa	VPK
System name	BES (betonielementtisyseemi)	BES
Production year	Building completion year 1977 is used	1977C

A multi-storey and multi-family residential building (**RE2**) in the Suvela neighborhood within the municipality of Espoo, Finland (**FI**). Designed by the architectural office of Kalevi Ruokosuo and completed in **1977C**. A typical example of a building based on the open Finnish industry-standard **BES** system, based on cross-wall frame (**CW**) and so-called 'long slabs', a general name for both prestressed U-slabs and prestressed hollow-core slabs as used in this case. The building was constructed by 'Rakennuskunta **Haka**' using mostly components produced at its factory in the municipality of Vantaa, more specifically the district of Piispankylä (**VPK**), with additional components coming from Partek (likely Hyrylä factory) in case of the Variax 5 type hollow-core slabs and A-Elementti Oy Rakennusmies (likely Lohja factory) in case of the helical stair elements.

4.2.1. Selected element facets

Variax 5 hollow core slab

HS_FI_PRTK_PKHY_1977C

Figure 12. Cross sectional dimensions of the Variax 5 hollow-core slab.
Image source: BES-järjestelmän rakenteita koskeva suositus (1979)

Facet	Explanation	Code
Element type	Hollow-core slab	SH
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Partek Oy	PRTK
Factory (2 possibilities)	Paraisten Kalkki Oy in Hyrylä. 35 km from factory to site. The best guess.	PKHY
	Elementtituote Oy (original name) in Nastola. 131 km from factory to site.	ETNA
Production year	Building completion year 1977 is used	1977C

When the BES system was published in 1970 the terms 'long slab', or the technically incorrect but even more common 'long beam', were used as a general name for two types of prestressed slab elements, the U-slab under the brand name 'Nilcon' and the hollow-core

slab under brand names ‘Spiroll’, and ‘Variax’, which is shown below. The ‘long slabs’ can be seen as the main component of BES system, as evidenced by the fact that buildings built with the system were colloquially called ‘long beam houses’ in the 1970s.

The Variax 5 hollow core slabs are 1200 mm wide, following the BES standards dimensions, 265 mm thick, and spanning up to 13 meters, with number or prestressing tendons varying from 4 to 10, depending on the desired span. The number ‘5’ refers to the number of hollow cores in the slab. The slabs were originally introduced to the market in 1970 by Elementtiteute Oy, which was acquired in 1971 by Paraisten Kalkki Oy, later known as Partek Oy, and through a series of mergers and acquisitions today part of Parma Oy.

Haka balcony unit (combined slab and railing)

X_FI_HAKA_HKVP_1977

Figure 13. Element drawing of the balcony unit. Reproduced from Espoo city archive (Espoon kaupunginarkisto).

Facet	Explanation	Code
Element type	Balcony unit, L-shaped element combining slab and railing	XX
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Rakennuskunta Haka Oy	HAKA
Factory	Haka's factory in the municipality of Vantaa, Piispankylä district.	HKVP
Production year	Building completion year 1977	1977C

A typical balcony element used with BES construction. The BES study (BES-järjestelmän rakenteita koskeva suositus, 1979) did not standardise the components for balconies. This means that the balconies used in BES buildings have significant differences depending on the manufacturers. The one below should be taken as merely an example of a balcony unit used with BES. The balcony units in this case were supported by side walls standing on their own foundations and anchored through the exterior walls to the hollow-core slabs of the building's intermediate floors.

Staircase massive / ribbed / edge beam slab

SX_FI_HAKA_HKVP_1977C

Figure 14. Element drawing of the slab.
Reproduced from Espoo city archive (Espoon kaupunginarkisto).

Facet	Explanation	Code
Element type	Special slab defying classification. (Slab, other?)	SX
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Rakennuskunta Haka Oy	HAKA
Factory	Haka's factory in the municipality of Vantaa, Piispankylä district.	HKVP
Production year	Building completion year 1977	1977C

A particularly multiform slab type defying clear classification. Used for staircases in the project. Generally, a 100 mm thick massive slab has edge beams on sides that are 265 mm high, corresponding with the thickness of hollow core slabs. On one side, the edge beam is wider and includes indents for the connection of the helical stair components that are supported by the edge beam.

4. 3. Finland: LBU

Uusikylä, Tampere

CS_RE2_FI_AUSA-TVE_LBU_1971C

Figure 15. Left to right, top to bottom: 1) Element layout. Reproduced from the Tampere building control archive (Tampereen rakennusvalvonnan arkisto). 2) Photograph of installation. Reproduced from *Betonielementtirakenteet* (1977) 3) Patent section, plan, and illustration. Reproduced from Saارين (1969); 4) Photograph of the current situation (courtesy of Tapio Kaasalainen/TAU).

Facet	Explanation	Code
Structural principle	Cell system	CS
Building typology	Residential (multi-family)	RE2
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Ausa Ky	AUSA
Factory	Factory in Vehmainen district of Tampere	TVE
System name	LBU (Lohja Box Unit)	LBU
Production year	1971, the completion year of the first building	1971C

Facet	Explanation	Code
Element type	Box unit made of 4 panels, plus sandwich panels at ends.	X
Country code	Finland	FI
Manufacturer	Ausa Ky	AUSA
Factory	Ausa Ky's factory in Tampere, Vehmainen district	ATVE
Production year	Building completion year 1977	1977C

Individual box units were assembled at factory from a floor panel, a roof panel and two wall panels made of reinforced concrete, forming a tunnel that interlocks on all sides to adjacent box units. Sandwich panels were added on one or both ends of the tunnel. All interior work was done at the factory and only the installation of the box units and connecting the technical systems was done on the construction site.

4. 4. The Netherlands: VAM

Overvecht, Utrecht

CW_RE2_NL_IVAM-UTR_VAM_1968C

Figure 17. Left: Axonometric drawing of a residential unit built with the VAM system. Right: construction and finished buildings in Utrecht. Reproduced from van Elk & Priemus (1971).

The Marzahn residential area (**RE2**) in Berlin, Germany, was developed in 1974 using an integral-wall frame (**IW**) system with transverse and longitudinal load-bearing walls, and solid slabs. The neighbourhood was constructed by VEB Wohnungsbaukombinat (**VWBK**) employing the Wohnungsbauserie (**WBS-70**).

5. Discussion and concluding remarks

This report presents the development and implementation of a taxonomic classification for precast concrete, providing a structured framework for identifying and organising historical and technical information for reuse purposes. The purpose of this taxonomic classification is to facilitate the creation of a database of precast elements available for reuse – an upcoming ReCreate deliverable, D1.4. The proposed classification system aims to provide a common framework to organise precast elements and systems from different backgrounds into a common schema. This framework is based on a faceted approach in combination with enumerative categories. It overlaps with widely adopted standards for BIM.

To achieve this, the identified elements are first compiled into element classes describing an element type with generic properties, which is referred to as a **'blank' element**. When these elements are linked to a particular physical element with an ID and other specific properties such as location, surveying, and testing results, they can be stored in a separate database as **'donor building' elements**, which can be made digitally available to be included in the design process. Conversely, the taxonomy can be used to classify elements found in potential donor buildings and compare them with identified elements in the reuse database. In the case no match is found, the taxonomy provides a framework for creating new entries that can be compared with similar existing cases, contributing to enlarging the database over time.

Precast systems have evolved in diverse contexts. The industrialisation of prefabrication as a construction method required the development of standardisation and modularisation of design and assembly. While several analogies with natural history and species classification allow for an overall understanding of the development of precast systems, the analogy has limitations. Unlike biological evolution, which follows a gradual progression, these systems were developed according to industry needs, often dictated by national regulations or specific market conditions.

The development of the classification framework presented in this report has been discussed and consulted with experts within the ReCreate consortium. During this process, several historical classification systems were discussed to ensure the compatibility of the proposed schema. This process was based on a comparative analysis of case studies which highlighted the differences between the member countries. Although extensive classification systems are available, these are developed for conventional design processes. One of the main challenges encountered in developing the faceted system was addressing anomalies where classification criteria varied across different contexts. For example, categories leading to a clear distinction in one context could result in ambiguous terminology in other countries. A comparative analysis allowed for finding common denominators and compromises between usability and precision.

While faceted classification resolves many of the limitations associated with hierarchical structures, it also presents challenges. One key issue is the potential for incomplete classification due to insufficient data. Some elements and systems may lack the necessary information to be completely categorised across all facets, leading to gaps in the taxonomy. Another challenge is ensuring the taxonomy remains adaptable across different construction typologies, particularly for non-residential and hybrid building systems. Additionally, while structured classification facilitates data exchange, interoperability issues between different BIM platforms and industry-specific software remain a concern. Another challenge is maintaining the integrity of classification codes when GUIDs change with exports, requiring robust version control mechanisms to ensure data consistency.

The main limitation to scaling up the classification process is the digitalisation of historical documents, which are dispersed in specialised collections and archives. Furthermore, most of the original production companies no longer exist, and for those that are still operative, technical and market changes have made these technologies obsolete.

From a practical perspective, this classification framework will be useful for reuse projects, deconstruction audits, and circular economy initiatives. By systematically categorising precast elements, it becomes easier to assess quality, track provenance, and enable material reuse. The integration of metadata further supports documentation and retrieval, facilitating better decision-making throughout a building's lifecycle.

The development and implementation of the proposed classification system has provided a structured approach to categorising precast concrete elements within Building Information Modelling (BIM) environments. By aligning with internationally recognised standards such as ISO 12006-2, ISO 22274, and ISO 19650, the classification system ensures consistency and interoperability across different construction workflows. Furthermore, the use of hierarchical categories for different facets allows the creation of taxonomies of elements and systems while preserving the possibility of classifying an object into multiple categories without having to change the overall structure. This enables the flexible handling of particular cases that are difficult to accommodate in conventional tree-like classification schemas.

The structured classification of reclaimed precast concrete elements plays a crucial role in improving efficiency, sustainability, and traceability in modern reuse-based construction. By providing a standardised approach to categorisation, the system enhances BIM workflows, facilitates material reuse, and supports circular economy objectives. While limitations exist, ongoing refinements and advancements in digital tools will help overcome these challenges.

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7. Annexes

7.1. ISO 3166-1 A2 country codes

List of ISO codes for countries involved in ReCreate.

ISO 3166-1 A2	Country	Status	Mapping status
FI	Finland	Member country	Mapped
SE	Sweden	Member country	Mapped
DE	Germany	Member country	Mapped
NL	Netherlands	Member country	Mapped
HR	Croatia	Member country	Not included in the mapping
BG	Bulgaria	Target country	Mapped
CZ	Czechia	Target country	Mapped
EE	Estonia	Target country	Mapped
HU	Hungary	Target country	Partially mapped
LT	Lithuania	Target country	Mapped
LV	Latvia	Target country	Mapped
PL	Poland	Target country	Mapped
RO	Romania	Target country	Mapped
SK	Slovakia	Target country	Partially mapped

7.2. Swedish naming system for concrete elements

The elements are typically designated a code with three capital letters (1, 2, and 3) according to the table below followed by a slash (/) and additional capital letters for execution (4). The nominal dimensions of the cross-section are specified with numbers (5). Finally, any reinforcement variant (6) is indicated. The order is as follows:

Letter	Contour	Section	Product type	Execution
-				Slakarmerat <i>Slack</i> <i>(conventional)</i> <i>reinforcement</i>
A				
B			Balkar <i>beams</i>	
C				
D			Däckelement <i>Floor elements</i>	Däcksupptagande <i>(uppstickande</i> <i>byglär)</i> <i>Floor load-bearing</i> <i>(protruding</i> <i>stirrups)</i>
E			Balkonger <i>Balconies</i>	Efterspänt <i>Post-tensioned</i>
F				Förspänt <i>Pre-tensioned</i>
G			Grundläggningselement <i>Foundation elements</i>	
H				Halv profil, ensidig <i>Half-profile, one-</i> <i>sided</i>
I				Isolerat <i>Insulated</i>
K				För kontinuitet <i>For continuity</i>
L				
M			Trappor <i>Cladding elements</i>	
N				
O				
P			Pelare <i>Columns</i>	Överhöjd- kompenserat <i>Overheight-</i> <i>compensated</i>
Q			Specialelement <i>Special elements</i>	
R				
S				Stålfot <i>Steel base</i>

T		Vid dubbelt T-snitt	
U			Ursparingslåda <i>Recess box</i>
V			Bärande väggelement <i>Load-bearing wall elements</i>
W			Sandwichelement <i>Sandwich elements</i>
X			Ej standardarm <i>Non-standard reinforcement</i>
Y			Beklädnadselement <i>Cladding elements</i>
Z			Pålar <i>Piles</i>

7.3. Finnish naming system for concrete elements

Element Type	Element	ID
Foundation elements	Footing element	A
	Pillar sleeve element	PH
	Foundation wall element (non-load-bearing)	AN
	Foundation wall element (load-bearing)	AS
	Ground beam	AK
	Foundation wall element (ground pressure)	AR
	Foundation wall (ground pressure, single leaf)	AV
	Retaining wall element	TKE
Column elements	Column	P
Wall elements	Partition wall	V
	Partition wall (deep beam)	VSP
	Square panel (exterior wall, load-bearing)	S

	Square panel (exterior wall, non-load-bearing)	R
	Inner leaf element (exterior wall, load-bearing)	SK
	Inner leaf element (exterior wall, non-load-bearing)	RK
	Inner leaf element (exterior wall, load-bearing, insulation + plastering)	SKR
	Inner leaf element (exterior wall, non-load-bearing, insulation + plastering)	RKR
	Strip panel (exterior wall, load-bearing)	NK
	Strip panel (exterior wall, non-load-bearing)	N
	Outer leaf element (exterior wall)	KE
Beam elements	Beam element (reinforced concrete)	K
	Prestressed beam (I-profile)	I
	Prestressed beam (HI-, meaning ridged I-profile)	HI
	Prestressed beam (other profiles)	JK ⁽¹⁾
Slab elements	Floor slab element (massive)	L
	Base floor slab (massive, insulated)	EL
	Prestressed slab element	JL
	Hollow-core slab	O/P ⁽²⁾
	Composite floor plank	KL
	TT-slab	TT
	HTT-slab (Ridged TT, roof unit)	HTT
Balcony elements	Balcony element	C
	Balcony slab element	CL
	Prestressed balcony slab element	JCL
	Cantilevering balcony slab	UCL
	Balcony side wall element	M
	Balcony railing element	Z
	The balcony roof element	CX

	Prestressed balcony roof element	JCX
Stair elements	Stair element	T
Elevator shaft elements	Elevator shaft element	HK ⁽³⁾
	Elevator shaft bottom element	HKA
	Elevator shaft top element	HKY
Special elements	Technical shaft element	H
	Special instance	.. X ⁽⁴⁾

- 1) JK can be used for coding prestressed rectangular, L, inverted T, or cross profiled beams.
- 2) The codes for hollow-core slabs include a number to denote the height of the slab. E.g. 370 mm high hollow-core slab is coded O37. Prefix (O, P, etc.) differs by manufacturer. The prefix also indicates the type of the slab, such as bathroom or insulated type slab. Manufacturer's design manual should be followed for correct coding.
- 3) An identifier denoting the shape of the unit can be added, e.g. HKU is an elevator shaft element with a U-shaped horizontal cross-section, while HKL is similarly L-shaped.
- 4) The code of an element deviating from the norm is appended with X. For example, if a project has a single massive slab unit (L) with a height differentiating from other similar units, it might be coded LX.